

Solving an Unrelated Parallel Machines Scheduling Problem with machine- and job-dependent setups and precedence constraints considering Support Machines

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Abstract

Single-stage production planning problems are common in the academic literature and in real-world environments. One of the least studied scenarios in the literature for this environment is that with Unrelated Parallel Machines. In this work, this type of problem is inspired by a real station within the wind tower production process. The problem presents characteristics that have already been studied, such as mandatory precedences and setup times that depend on the machine and the job. However, a new and real feature is presented: the existence of "support machines", which are machines that can continue to work but cannot complete jobs due to reduced capacity for some operational reason. In this case, instead of abandoning their work, support machines can still be used to assist other machines by performing partial jobs before handing them over to full-capacity machines for completion. This innovative concept of support machines, never before presented in this context of production planning, introduces a unique approach to dealing with reduced-capacity machines without sacrificing their operational potential. A Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) model is formulated to mathematically represent this problem.

This work explores the impact of these support machines on production planning. For this purpose, Tabu Search and Simulated Annealing meta-heuristics have been adapted for their solution, and a novel Constructive Heuristic has been developed based on the real and manual process currently

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performed in the aforementioned factory. These three algorithms are run and compared on a real database in order to minimise the makespan. Their analysis shows that although the use of support machines generally gives positive results, an improvement is not achieved in all cases. Furthermore, contrary to what might be expected, the use of full-capacity machines in the role of support machines sometimes improves completion times.

Keywords: Scheduling, Unrelated Parallel Machines, Support Machines, Constructive Heuristic, Tabu Search, Simulated Annealing

1. Introduction

Single-stage production planning problems are not only very present in the scientific literature but also have an extensive practical application (Huang et al., 2022; Rafiei et al., 2017). This application is not only focused on situations with a single stage; it also extends to more complex problems with multiple stages (Muñoz-Díaz et al., 2022). There are two main scenarios where this situation occurs. The first is when multiple stages are available but can be decomposed into simpler single-stage problems that are independent or weakly linked (Pinto and Grossmann, 1995). The second occurs in multi-stage production processes where there is a significant bottleneck that causes the throughput of the entire plant to depend on that single stage. The planning and scheduling of operations at such stations has been a fundamental problem in production management for decades (Hum and Sarin, 1991) and, in several real cases, only the bottleneck station is modelled in order to subsequently extend this planning to the rest of the stations (Hiremath et al., 2022; Hao and Lin, 2021; Aguirre and Papageorgiou, 2018; Liu et al., 2008; Marchetti and Cerdá, 2009).

One of the most frequent environments in single-stage production planning is parallel machine problems, where there are multiple machines and all of them can process any of the jobs. This type of problem has three main variants: Identical Parallel Machines, where the processing time of each job is the same on all machines; Uniform Parallel Machines, where the processing times depend on the speed of each machine and finally; Unrelated Parallel Machines, where the processing times depend on the speed of each machine and the speed of each machine depends not only on the machine where a job is carried out, but also on the job itself (Brucker, 2007).

In this work, we will solve the production planning problem for a single

stage, more specifically, for Unrelated Parallel Machines. In addition, a real and novel feature identified in a factory producing wind towers is considered: the existence of machines with the same functionalities as the rest, but without enough capacity to finish the complete jobs. These machines are not obsolete and work perfectly, but due to the evolution of the final product, they cannot anymore perform 100% of the job assigned to each job. These machines, like the others, can start any job and remain a valuable resource, so they can start any job and then transfer the unfinished work to another available machine at full capacity.

Nowadays, due to the rapid advancement of technology, this situation can often be found in very different areas. This can be due to the capacity of the machine itself, the capacity of the means of transport between the machine and the next station, or the availability of working space on the machine. A clear example of the first of these is additive manufacturing, a process known for its layer-by-layer construction technique. Additive manufacturing has experienced a very rapid advance in its scope and consequently in the size of the parts it produces. Although larger sizes can often be achieved with this technology through the use of assembly of smaller parts, this is not always possible or optimal. Therefore, smaller printers can be used to support larger printers by supplying the smallest parts.

Assembly processes are a clear example of a case where the capacity of the machine is actually reduced due to the capacity of the means of transport downstream of the machine. A more concrete example would be the use of cranes that link two stages of a production system. If the weight of the parts increases, machines that rely on cranes with lower capacity to transfer finished pieces to the next point in the production system will also experience a reduction in their operational capacity. In this case, again, machines with this limitation will be able to perform part of the production process and, before reaching the weight limit of their corresponding crane, send the part to another machine with sufficient capacity.

Finally, a concrete example of the situation in which available workstation space becomes a constraint is in wind tower manufacturing. Wind towers, one of the main parts of wind turbines (Tsai et al., 2016), are constantly evolving, with increasingly taller towers being produced. This could mean that not all welding machines in a plant with a previously designed layout have enough space to produce complete tower sections. In this case, the machines with this limitation produce sections until the limit length is reached, and send the semi-finished sections to one of the other machines with full capacity.

In any of the above cases, there is a limitation in the problem that means that, although some machines can execute exactly the same functionalities as the rest of the machines in the station, they cannot finish the entire job. These machines will be considered as support machines for those that are capable of performing 100% of any job. This results in an Unrelated Parallel Machine Scheduling Problem with Support Machines.

For the solving of this problem, which will be described in depth in the following section, three different methodologies are provided in this work: an adaptation of Tabu Search and Simulated Annealing that solves exactly the same problem; and a Constructive Heuristic completely tailored to the problem itself. The three methodologies are compared below using the same data set.

The subsequent sections of this paper are structured as follows. Section 2 outlines the problem and situates it within the existing literature. Section 3 presents and explains in detail the three different methodologies used to address the problem. Section 4 is dedicated to the presentation and analysis of the results obtained through the application of these methodologies. Finally, Section 5 presents the main conclusions drawn from the results and Section 6 provides a complete list of the references cited throughout this document.

2. Problem definition and related works

In this paper, a single-stage production planning problem is solved. In the analysed station there are widely studied characteristics, but also one that stands out for its novelty in the literature and for its important application in practise. To facilitate the understanding of the problem, we first present the key feature of this problem, the support machines, and then describe the rest of the problem in depth.

2.1. Support Machines

As mentioned above, there are several machines in the stage under study that are capable of performing exactly the same functions, but not all of them have the capacity to handle the complete jobs that are being processed at present. However, they are machines that work in perfect conditions and are used to support the other machines. In this way, the machines that do not have the capacity to process complete jobs, from now on called Support Machines (SMs), will start the process performed in that station, and when they have reached their maximum capacity, they will transfer the jobs to

Figure 1: Diagram of the real scenario for a situation with N MMs and S SMs

the machines with full capacity, from now on called Main Machines (MMs). When a SM transfers a job to a MM, a transport time is added between the two operations, and there is no additional setup time before the job is taken over by the MM. A schematic representation of the situation can be seen in Figure 1 and, for the sake of clarity, the group of SMs is represented as a single box (SMs). This box, although it appears repeatedly, always represents the same group of machines: $SM 1, SM 2, \dots, SM S$.

This characteristic means that not every machine can process any job completely, an essential characteristic in Parallel Machines problems (Kai and Shanlin, 2008; Kamath, 2011; Lee, 1991). Therefore, the problem cannot be characterised as a classic Parallel Machines problem in any of its versions.

Given this situation, the option of characterising this problem as a Hybrid Flow Shop, also known in the literature as Flexible Flow Shop or Multi-processor Flow Shop (Mousavi et al., 2018), is proposed. These problems were first introduced by Arthanari and Ramamurthy (1971) and Salvador (1973), who defined them as a generalisation of the classical Flow Shop but having at least one of its stations with multiple machines. In this case, the problem was to assign jobs to each of these machines and to sequence the groups of jobs assigned to each machine. Adapting the real problem presented here to this type of problem, a scheme like the one shown in Figure 2 would result. In this diagram, in order to maintain the presentation adopted in Figure 1, the box labelled SMs again represents the group of SMs.

Adopting the definition of Hybrid Flow Shop, henceforth HFS, it should

Figure 2: Diagram of the scenario as a Flow Shop with S SMs in the first station and N MMs in the second station

be taken into account that, in our problem, not all jobs would pass through the SM station. This characteristic has already been studied for HFS and is called Stage Skipping (Behnamian et al., 2014; Defersha, 2015; Javadian et al., 2012). Çolak and Keskin (2022) define this term as the characteristic that gives flexibility to these problems by the possibility that certain jobs are not processed at certain stages of an HFS problem. However, in this type of problem, it is known in advance which jobs will skip which stations, in contrast to the present problem. For the problem solved here, the algorithm itself will choose which jobs are processed in an SM and which jobs are not, so it is not an input but an output of the production scheduling. Furthermore, the production times at station II (Figure 2) would depend on whether the job to be processed at each MM has been previously processed by a SM or not. Again, these characteristics make it impossible to model this problem as an HFS with Stage Skipping.

With this in mind and although similar problems have been solved previously in the literature, there is no literature that covers the feature presented here. Therefore, the problem presented here involves a single station with parallel machines (MM) and a series of extra machines (SM) that can process any of the jobs, but none of them can process a job in its entirety. These SMs, once they finish the part they can handle, supply their semi-finished jobs to one of the MMs for completion. In other words, the SMs work in support of the other MMs. This gives rise to a production scheduling problem of single-stage production and parallel machines supported by another set of

parallel machines with the same functions but not the same capacity.

2.2. Problem Characteristics

Knowing now that there are two separate groups of machines, the set of MMs and the set of SMs, both of them, independently, do adapt to the definition of Parallel Machines. Also, based on the characteristics of the real industries mentioned above, the processing times of each job do not depend only on the MM where it is carried out, but also on the job to be processed itself. This turns the problem into an Unrelated Parallel Machine Problem (Brucker, 2007). More specifically, we are going to consider machines on which the speed depends on a specific property of the jobs to be processed, having machines on which the production speed will improve with the value of that property, and machines on which it will decrease. A real example of this, based on the wind tower manufacturing process that has motivated this study, is when the welding speed depends on the thickness of the plate to be welded. There are machines that increase their efficiency with large thicknesses and machines that increase it with small thicknesses (Lorenzo-Espejo et al., 2022). Hereinafter, this property will be referred to as Decisive Feature (DF). Lorenzo-Espejo et al. (2022) analyse the impact of this and other potential DFs on the wind turbine tower manufacturing process.

Therefore, in this work, three types of MMs will be considered based on their response to changes in DF. They are listed below and the nomenclature for the sets of machines is defined:

- Positive response to an increase in DF.
These machines will belong to the MM_A set.
- Not influenced by DF.
These machines will belong to the MM_B set.
- Positive response to a decrease in DF.
These machines will belong to the MM_C set.

At this point, it is important to note that many of the jobs to be performed will be exactly the same. That is, there will be jobs with identical characteristics, including the value of DF. This is known as High Multiplicity, a term that was coined by Hochbaum and Shamir (1990, 1991) and had also previously been studied by Psaraftis (1980). High Multiplicity Scheduling Problems are those where there are different types of jobs for which we have

the number of jobs of each type and the attributes that represent all the jobs of each type (Brauner et al., 2005). In this paper, it is considered that all job types have the same number of jobs and that there are n job types.

On the other hand, there are setups that are not sequence-dependent but machine- and job-dependent. In addition, there are a number of mandatory precedences between some of the jobs to be executed, which therefore force these jobs to be executed on the same machine. Ultimately, the objective of this problem is to allocate and sequence jobs while minimising the makespan (Kim and Lee, 2021; Soares and Carvalho, 2022).

Finally, the conditions and assumptions considered in this problem are presented below:

- All jobs and machines are available at time zero
- Buffer capacity between SM and MM machines unlimited
- The problem data is deterministic and known in advance
- All sets of job types have the same number of jobs
- Release time for all jobs equal to 0
- All machines are always available
- Transport time between machines is independent of the machine pair
- Raw material, staff and other resources are always available. No interruptions, unforeseen breakdowns, or reprocessing

With all this, we have an Unrelated Parallel Machine Scheduling Problem with Support Machines (UPMSP-SM). This problem can be classified according to Graham et al. (1979) as a $R - PSM|prec, S_{i,j}|C_{max}$, where $R-PSM$ means that the main machines are Unrelated Parallel Machines (R) and the Support Machines are Identical Parallel Machine (PSM), $prec$ the presence of precedences, $S_{i,j}$ the existence of machine- and job-dependent setup times and, finally, C_{max} indicates the Objective Function of the problem, minimising the maximum completion time.

It should be noted that, although it is not relevant for this work because different configurations of the same problem will be analysed, the number of machines could be known. In this case, as is often the situation with this nomenclature, the number of machines of each type would be given before

the acronyms indicating the type of machine. For example, for four MMs and one SM, the problem would be characterised as $4R-1PSM|prec, S_{i,j}|C_{max}$.

2.3. Mixed-Integer Linear Programming Model

The mathematical formulation for the aforementioned problem is provided below. First, the parameters and indices are presented along with the decision variables in the problem (Table 1).

Table 1: Parameters, indexes, and variables of the model

Parameters and indexes	
N	Set of MMs
S	Set of SMs
J	Set of jobs
J^+	Set of jobs, including a dummy job named 0
p_{ik}	Processing time of job i on machine k
ps_{ik}	Processing time of job i on main machine k when the job is supported
st_{ik}	Setup time of job i on machine k
tt	Transport time
z_{ij}	Binary parameter for mandatory precedences. $z_{ij} = 1$ if job j must be processed immediately after i , otherwise 0.
M	Very large number
Variables	
c_i	Completion time of job i
cs_i	Completion time of job i in support machine (if job i is supported)
C_{max}	Maximum Completion Time: Makespan
x_{ijk}	Binary variable. $x_{ijk} = 1$ if job i is scheduled immediately before the job j on main machine k , otherwise 0.
y_{ijk}	Binary variable. $y_{ijk} = 1$ if job i is scheduled immediately before the job j on support machine k , otherwise 0.
y_i	Binary variable. $y_i = 1$ if job i is supported, otherwise 0.

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{Min } C_{max} & \tag{1} \\
\text{s.a. } C_{max} \geq c_i & \quad \forall i \in J \tag{2} \\
\sum_{j \in J^+} x_{0jk} = 1 & \quad \forall k \in N \tag{3} \\
\sum_{j \in J^+} y_{0jk} = 1 & \quad \forall k \in S \tag{4} \\
\sum_{k \in N} \sum_{i \in J^+ \setminus \{j\}} x_{ijk} = 1 & \quad \forall j \in J \tag{5} \\
\sum_{k \in S} \sum_{i \in J^+ \setminus \{j\}} y_{ijk} \leq 1 & \quad \forall j \in J \tag{6} \\
\sum_{i \in J^+ \setminus \{j\}} x_{ijk} = \sum_{l \in J^+ \setminus \{j\}} x_{jlk} & \quad \forall j \in J; \forall k \in N \tag{7} \\
\sum_{i \in J^+ \setminus \{j\}} y_{ijk} = \sum_{l \in J^+ \setminus \{j\}} y_{jlk} & \quad \forall j \in J; \forall k \in S \tag{8} \\
\sum_{k \in N} x_{ijk} \geq z_{ij} & \quad \forall i, j \in J \tag{9} \\
y_j = \sum_{i \in J^+} \sum_{k \in S} y_{ijk} & \quad \forall j \in J \tag{10} \\
c_j \geq c_i + st_{jk} + (1 - y_j)p_{jk} & \\
+ y_j \cdot ps_{jk} - M(1 - x_{ijk}) & \quad \forall i \in J^+; \forall j \in J; \forall k \in N \tag{11} \\
cs_j \geq cs_i + st_{jk} + p_{jk} - M(1 - y_{ijk}) & \quad \forall i \in J^+; \forall j \in J; \forall k \in S \tag{12} \\
c_j \geq cs_j + tt + st_{jk} + ps_{jk} & \\
- M(1 - y_j) - M \left(1 - \sum_{i \in J^+} x_{ijk} \right) & \quad \forall j \in J; \forall k \in N \tag{13} \\
c_0 = 0; cs_0 = 0 & \tag{14} \\
c_i, cs_i \geq 0 & \quad \forall i \in J \tag{15} \\
x_{ijk} \in \{0, 1\} & \quad \forall i, j \in J^+; \forall k \in N \tag{16} \\
y_{ijk}, y_i \in \{0, 1\} & \quad \forall i, j \in J^+; \forall k \in S \tag{17}
\end{aligned}$$

The objective function to be minimised, the maximum completion time, is given in Constraint (1), and Constraints (2) ensure that the maximum completion time is greater than or equal to the completion time of each job. A dummy job is introduced in Constraints (3) and (4), which indicate that the dummy job 0 is placed at the beginning of each main and support machine, respectively. Constraints (5) ensure that each job is assigned to a single main machine and has one immediately preceding job. Similarly, Constraints (6) ensure that each job is assigned to at most one support machine and has at most one immediately preceding job. Balance equations for main and support machines are included by Constraints (7) and (8). Constraints (9) are enforced to ensure that the mandatory sequences between certain job pairs are met and Constraints (10) introduce the decision variables that establish whether a job is supported or not. Regarding the definition of completion times for each job, Constraints (11) and (12) define them for each job on the main and support machines, respectively, taking into account the completion times of the immediately preceding job, setup times, and processing times. Furthermore, Constraints (13) take into account the transport time for jobs supported on support machines and completed on the main machines, and Constraints (14) define the completion times for the dummy job on the main and support machines. Finally, Constraints (15), (16) and (17) are the basic constraints on the decision variables.

3. Resolution methodologies

Before starting to explain the solving methodologies proposed here, a theorem is presented to prove that the present problem is NP-hard.

Theorem 1. *Problem $R - PSM|prec, S_{i,j}|C_{max}$ is NP-hard.*

Karp (1972) proved that the problem classified as $R||C_{max}$ is NP-hard in the strong sense, even with only two machines. Therefore, according to the complicated theoretic (Li et al., 2013a,b), $R - PSM|prec, S_{i,j}|C_{max}$ problem is also NP-hard.

Given the NP-hard character of the problem, which indicates that the existence of a polynomial bounded algorithm to solve the problem is highly unlikely (Potts, 1985), this paper presents three alternatives to solve it with realistic problem sizes. These methodologies provide good, although not

necessarily optimal, solutions in reasonable computational times. The first two algorithms, given the lack of literature covering the present problem, are an adaptation of Tabu Search and Simulated Annealing metaheuristics to the characteristics described in the previous section. The third is a Constructive Heuristic developed specifically for the problem under consideration. All algorithms provide an answer to the same problem and are compared in the following sections.

3.1. Tabu Search

Tabu search is a trajectory-based metaheuristic proposed by Glover (1986). It operates through an iterative search process within the neighbourhood of the solution, addressing the potential risk of convergence to a local optimum by prohibiting or penalising certain moves. These moves are included in a list known as the *tabu list*, which remains in effect for a certain period of time, called the *tabu tenure*. The tabu moves include the most recent actions taken. Consequently, the algorithm restricts moves to solutions that have been visited recently, thereby avoiding cyclic scenarios. However, if the resulting solution exceeds the performance of previous ones, the move is allowed, which constitutes an aspiration criterion.

This technique has already been adapted to numerous production planning problems (Sun et al., 2022; Gnatowski et al., 2022; Suppiah et al., 2022). In this subsection, the characteristics of Tabu Search implemented to solve the present problem are presented.

For all instances of the problem, 1000 iterations have been performed, while the size of the Tabu list has depended on the number of jobs in each of the instances. For the generation of new neighbourhoods, six different movements have been executed: *Swap Machines*, *Swap Jobs in Machine*, *Swap Jobs between Machines*, *Insertion*, *Remove Job*, and *Add Job*.

Starting with movements involving pairs of machines, *Swap Machines* exchanges the assignment between two machines, all jobs assigned to one machine will be assigned to the other, and vice versa; *Swap Jobs between Machines* takes two jobs from two different machines and exchanges them; and, finally, *Insertion* subtracts a job from one machine and inserts it into another. All these movements can be made between two MMs or between two SMs.

On the other hand, regarding to the movements that involve only one machine, *Swap Jobs in Machine* takes two jobs assigned to the same machine and exchanges their positions, and this is done in both MMs and SMs;

Remove Job removes a job from the SM; and *Add Job* adds a job to an SM. These last two movements are obviously only performed in the assignments of the SMs.

3.2. Simulated Annealing

Simulated Annealing is an optimisation algorithm inspired by the advantages of gradually cooling metals to improve their quality. Similarly, at each virtual temperature, the algorithm generates new solutions that are neighbours of the current solution. The acceptance of these new solutions follows the Metropolis criterion (Kirkpatrick et al., 1983), where the probability of acceptance depends on the current temperature. This iterative process continues until the algorithm converges.

This technique is another widely used metaheuristic for production planning problems (Defersha et al., 2022; Hasani and Hosseini, 2022; Bektur, 2022). As in the previous section, this subsection characterises the Simulated Annealing algorithm used to solve the problem at hand. The initial (T_0) and final (T_f) temperatures have been set at 50 and 1, respectively. The number of iterations at each temperature level is 10, and according to the Cauchy formula for marking the temperature decrease (Szu and Hartley, 1987), the degree of temperature reduction or time step is characterised by $\alpha = 0.001$.

$$T_{i+1} = \frac{T_i}{1 + \alpha \cdot T_i} \quad (18)$$

Finally, for the generation of neighbourhoods, the same six movements explained for Tabu Search algorithm have been carried out: *Swap Machines*, *Swap Jobs in Machine*, *Swap Jobs between Machines*, *Insertion*, *Remove Job*, and *Add Job*.

3.3. Proposed Constructive Heuristic

This section presents a Constructive Heuristic for solving the problem presented in the previous section. This heuristic is divided into two blocks, the first one solves the allocation and sequencing of jobs in the MMs and the second one in the SMs. Both blocks solve the allocation and then identify the most appropriate sequence for each machine.

This heuristic is partly based on the procedure used in the industrial environment mentioned above. More specifically, the first block of the heuristic replicates the manual allocation that is currently performed. In this factory,

they rely solely on the DF to decide which jobs are sent to one MM or another.

The parameters used to elucidate this heuristic are in line with those previously established in the mathematical model (Table 1), but there are two new additions. These are outlined below:

N	Number of MMs
T	Number of job types

Heuristic for MMs

In this first block, the heuristic assigns both jobs and entire sets of jobs by type to reduce execution time. In order to facilitate the explanation of this heuristic, six labels are created, which will only be used for explanatory purposes in this document. These labels will designate jobs and sets of jobs according to their DF value, indicating which ones are selected from those that have not been assigned to a machine yet. The six labels are defined below:

JS_A	Job sets with the highest DF value among the remainder
JS_B	Job sets with DF values closest to the median among the remainder
JS_C	Job sets with the lowest DF value among the remainder
J_A	Jobs with the highest DF value among the remainder
J_B	Jobs with DF values closest to the median among the remainder
J_C	Jobs with the lowest DF value among the remainder

In cases where the number of different job types is sufficiently large compared to the number of available machines, the idea of the proposed heuristic is to first assign complete sets of job types, thus decreasing the execution time of the algorithm. For the assignments, the parameter DF and the characteristics of the machines in terms of that parameter will be taken into account, being able to assign complete sets because they share the value of DF.

For this purpose, if the number of job types (T) exceeds the number of MMs (N) by more than 50%, the X job sets with a higher (JS_A) and lower (JS_C) DF value will be assigned to the MMs with better conditions for

high (MM_A) and low (MM_C) DF, respectively (Figure 3). Where X is the value of the number of jobs between the number of MMs rounded down (19).

$$X = \left\lfloor \frac{T}{N} \right\rfloor \quad (19)$$

Next, if X is greater than 1, $X-1$ sets of JS_B jobs, i.e., those with values closest to the median of all remaining sets, will be assigned to the MMs with the best conditions for it (MM_B) (Figure 3). At this point, the algorithm stops working with sets and starts handling single jobs, having already assigned a large percentage of the jobs of the problem.

From here, a cycle begins and is repeated until all the jobs have been assigned to the MMs. These cycles determine which machine is the least loaded, identify which type of machine it is, and therefore which DF size is the most appropriate, and then assign a job of that size to that machine (Figure 3).

Finally, the allocation of each machine is rearranged according to the preferences of each production system. In this case, they are ordered by alternating orders according to their type; i.e., it is avoided that all products of the same type are produced in a row.

Heuristic for SMs

In the second block of the heuristic, the SMs will reduce the workload of the MMs. So in the cases where there are no SMs, this second block would not be applicable. However, whenever there is at least one SM, this second block is executed.

In this block, unlike the previous one, there are several cycles that are repeated under certain conditions, all of which can be seen in Figure 4 and are explained below.

The first of the cycles starts by searching for the machine with the highest load, storing it in *MLM1* and checking that it is not an SM. If *MLM1* is SM, it immediately exits the cycle and proceeds to readjust the SM allocations (Figure 4). If it is not, it looks for the least loaded SM, stores it in *LLSM* and looks for the last job in *MLM1* that is not yet supported by any SM. If there is no job in *MLM1* that is not yet supported, it would immediately exit the cycle and, again, proceed to readjust the SM allocations. In contrast, if there are jobs that are not yet supported, the last of these is chosen and assigned to *LLSM*. Finally in this cycle, the machine with the most load is

Figure 3: Diagram of Block I of the Constructive Heuristic

Figure 4: Diagram of Block II of the Constructive Heuristic

searched again, stored in *MLM2* and if the load of *MLM2* is less than the initial load of *MLM1* ($MLM1_0$), that is, before the last allocation to *LLSM*, the cycle is repeated again.

In cases where the load on *MLM2* is higher, the last assignment is removed and the job in *MLM1* with the shortest production time in *LLSM* that is not yet supported is searched for. This job is assigned to *LLSM*. Once again, the machine with the highest load at this time is searched for and stored in *MLM2*. If the *MLM2* load is greater than the initial *MLM1* load, the last assignment is removed again.

Next, the jobs assigned to any SM that were assigned as the first job to a MM are deleted, if they exist. This is done because, obviously, it is impossible for the SM to have the job ready at time 0 and then process it further in the MM. After this, the jobs of all the SMs are reordered according to their Completion Times in their corresponding MMs. Finally, it is checked that the Completion Time of each job in the SMs plus the transport time to the MMs is lower than the Completion Time of the previous job in the respective MM. If this is not the case, the job is removed from the SM to which it was assigned.

At this point, the algorithm stops and returns the allocation and sequence for each of the machines.

4. Analysis of Results

This section shows the results of the three algorithms. For this purpose, a data set based on the real industry mentioned above has been used. The data set has four different problem sizes and eight different resource configurations. The size of the problem refers to the number of jobs that the algorithms will assign and sequence. Problems with 100, 150, 200 and 300 jobs will be solved. The resource configurations refer to the number of MMs and SMs available in each problem (Table 2). Combining these two characteristics, a total of 32 different combinations are obtained.

Finally, each of these combinations is solved for five different data problems. This gives a total of 160 instances, the results of which are presented in four tables, one for each size. It is important to note that due to the random component of Tabu Search and Simulated Annealing algorithms, it would not be consistent to display the results of a single execution for each instance. For this reason, both algorithms were run a total of 10 times for each of the 160 instances. For each instance, the best value obtained, i.e. the

Table 2: Resource configurations for which the algorithms have been executed. *MM*: Number of Main Machines; *SM*: Number of Support Machines; *Code*: Code used in Tables 3, 4, 5, and 6 to reference each configuration.

MM	SM	Code
3	0	3MM 0SM
3	1	3MM 1SM
5	0	5MM 0SM
5	1	5MM 1SM
5	2	5MM 2SM
7	0	7MM 0SM
7	1	7MM 1SM
7	3	7MM 3SM

minimum makespan, is presented, as well as the mean of the ten makespans obtained for each instance and their standard deviation. In addition to presenting the results of each algorithm, its execution times are also shown in the *Runtime* columns, allowing for comparison of not only the final result, but also its applicability in industry.

Tables 3, 4, 5, and 6 show this information. The first column indicates the problem and instance presented in each row. The second and third columns are for the *Makespan* and *Runtime* of the Constructive Heuristic (*CH*). The next four columns show the best result (*Minimum*), mean (*Mean*), standard deviation (*SD*), and runtime (*Runtime*) for Tabu Search algorithm (*TS*). Finally, the last four columns show the same information as the previous four columns, but for the Simulated Annealing algorithm (*SA*). All algorithms were implemented in Python and solved on an Intel® Core™ i7-4790 CPU at 3.60 GHz with 12 GB of RAM using PyCharm Edu 2021.3.2.

First of all, by examining the four tables, both the best results and the average results with their standard deviations are analysed for each meta-heuristic (*TS* and *SA*), as well as the unique results obtained by the heuristic (*CH*). To make the tables easier to read, the best makespan for each instance, which is the smallest value between the *Minimum* and *Makespan* columns for each row, is shown in bold. In addition, Table 7 shows the percentage of instances for each size for which each algorithm returns the best makespan. Furthermore, the aggregated result for all 160 instances for each algorithm is shown in the *Aggregate* column. With all this information, it is easy to see that Tabu Search gives better results for the vast majority of instances, in

Table 3: Results of the problem with a size of 100 jobs. The times in the *Makespan*, *Minimum*, *Mean* and *SD* columns are in hours; the times in the *Runtime* columns are in seconds

Instances		CH		TS			SA				
		Makespan	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime
3M_0SM	1	330.3100	0.0782	324.2854	324.2854	0.0000	2.6203	324.2854	324.2854	0.0000	5.6472
	2	333.0520	0.0469	328.6236	328.6236	0.0000	2.6214	328.6236	328.6236	0.0000	5.7104
	3	332.7297	0.0156	328.1226	328.1226	0.0000	2.6337	328.1226	328.1226	0.0000	5.6913
	4	330.9501	0.0206	326.8847	326.8847	0.0000	2.6230	326.8847	326.8847	0.0000	5.6669
	5	330.9908	0.0307	327.2398	327.2398	0.0000	2.6334	327.2398	327.2398	0.0000	5.6554
3M_1SM	1	260.5131	0.0289	252.9632	252.9632	0.0000	4.6987	252.9632	259.5752	21.4661	12.1430
	2	262.2610	0.0287	257.0272	257.3914	0.3839	4.6407	257.0272	263.6022	21.5663	11.8881
	3	262.6373	0.0293	257.4326	264.8538	22.2373	4.4723	257.4326	263.9471	21.2866	11.8624
	4	260.5847	0.0303	255.3107	264.4317	21.9844	4.7692	255.3107	262.0682	21.5131	11.9533
	5	259.5588	0.0329	253.6461	268.3649	31.0298	4.7482	253.6461	253.6461	0.0000	12.0494
5M_0SM	1	192.2895	0.0228	182.5087	182.5087	0.0000	4.7595	182.5087	182.5087	0.0000	9.0908
	2	188.2439	0.0307	183.1573	183.1573	0.0000	4.8237	183.1573	183.1573	0.0000	9.1106
	3	194.4586	0.0310	181.2370	181.2370	0.0000	4.8169	181.2370	181.2370	0.0000	9.0576
	4	196.1214	0.0517	182.1571	182.1571	0.0000	4.8237	182.1571	182.1571	0.0000	9.1210
	5	190.7655	0.0228	182.1923	182.1923	0.0000	4.8217	182.1923	182.1923	0.0000	9.1097
5M_1SM	1	192.2895	0.0309	162.1427	164.5473	6.3511	6.9013	162.1427	168.2582	7.2656	15.3872
	2	188.2439	0.0312	163.6545	163.7583	0.2193	6.9491	163.6545	166.5765	4.2094	15.1860
	3	194.4586	0.0311	162.5710	170.3972	9.3935	6.8724	162.5710	168.4365	8.2733	15.4759
	4	196.1214	0.0627	161.6926	162.4008	1.0817	6.9092	161.8745	165.9599	4.7774	15.6011
	5	190.7655	0.0312	163.5839	163.6199	0.0170	6.9001	163.5839	166.7817	5.4835	15.5575
5M_2SM	1	164.9405	0.0393	156.2322	162.5580	10.7194	7.2692	155.0101	156.2632	0.7197	18.0365
	2	162.2231	0.0313	155.1768	159.0045	8.5381	7.3703	155.3081	156.5966	1.0865	17.7382
	3	168.1669	0.0625	156.1970	157.0123	1.2643	7.4207	156.1970	159.0955	7.3681	12.9519
	4	168.5405	0.0393	154.9164	155.6925	1.0989	5.5831	154.4351	156.4193	1.1227	17.9647
	5	163.1293	0.0313	155.2111	158.9575	8.2570	5.2288	155.2111	155.9625	0.6629	17.9799
7M_0SM	1	190.2333	0.0413	173.3259	173.3259	0.0000	8.1668	173.3259	173.3259	0.0000	14.5841
	2	188.2439	0.0312	175.4526	175.4526	0.0000	8.2517	175.4526	175.4526	0.0000	14.6009
	3	188.8599	0.0707	172.6844	172.6844	0.0000	8.2228	172.6844	172.6844	0.0000	14.6136
	4	188.4955	0.0391	172.1614	172.1614	0.0000	8.2329	172.1614	172.1614	0.0000	14.6311
	5	189.1392	0.0382	175.2583	175.2583	0.0000	8.1860	175.2583	175.2583	0.0000	14.5843
7M_1SM	1	162.7987	0.0390	149.7108	150.0389	1.0377	8.6329	149.7108	149.9565	0.5467	21.6112
	2	161.8521	0.0520	151.5451	151.5717	0.0841	10.3553	151.5451	157.4546	10.2184	22.0261
	3	162.5682	0.0314	150.0179	150.5350	0.9347	10.2659	150.0179	150.2367	0.4867	21.5831
	4	162.2626	0.0404	147.7133	152.6029	10.3082	10.3728	147.7133	150.6846	7.3198	21.3698
	5	162.1855	0.0325	151.6185	151.7961	0.4308	8.4929	151.6185	153.3074	5.1030	21.3311
7M_3SM	1	162.7987	0.0718	149.7108	152.6531	7.3247	11.0764	149.7108	149.7889	0.2589	27.4376
	2	161.8521	0.0417	151.5451	151.5556	0.0332	11.0779	151.5451	153.7185	7.2084	19.1496
	3	162.5682	0.0416	150.0179	150.0179	0.0000	9.4792	150.0179	150.0179	0.0000	27.4496
	4	162.2626	0.0631	147.7133	150.8215	7.6238	11.0666	147.7133	149.9358	7.3714	27.2099
	5	162.1855	0.0403	151.6185	151.6185	0.0000	10.9842	151.6185	155.9167	9.5627	27.5574

Table 4: Results of the problem with a size of 150 jobs. The times in the *Makespan*, *Minimum*, *Mean* and *SD* columns are in hours; the times in the *Runtime* columns are in seconds

Instances		CH		TS			SA				
		Makespan	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime
3M_0SM	1	469.3799	0.0207	447.8596	447.8596	0.0000	6.0496	447.8596	447.8596	0.0000	13.2787
	2	460.4701	0.0228	448.9937	448.9937	0.0000	5.8443	448.9937	449.0044	0.0354	13.2759
	3	467.9006	0.0308	449.2535	449.2535	0.0000	6.0268	449.2535	449.3369	0.2768	13.2198
	4	467.6713	0.0305	451.0166	451.0166	0.0000	6.0229	451.0166	451.0166	0.0000	13.3304
	5	461.8063	0.0625	448.8068	448.9613	0.2506	6.0016	448.8068	448.8868	0.1780	13.0823
3M_1SM	1	367.3970	0.0308	350.7316	351.2217	0.4414	11.6574	350.7316	353.7215	4.9813	32.1886
	2	384.8563	0.0226	352.2377	352.5188	0.3756	11.5372	352.0913	357.0889	8.5163	32.4129
	3	392.0330	0.0241	352.4798	362.6902	30.4176	11.8914	352.1060	353.6221	0.8283	32.2821
	4	366.4126	0.0303	352.1971	362.9374	30.9570	11.5932	352.9315	368.3961	28.8574	32.4336
	5	360.6413	0.0311	349.8404	361.0805	30.8331	11.4471	349.8404	354.6003	7.2812	32.4773
5M_0SM	1	289.5319	0.0704	273.1684	273.1684	0.0000	9.5748	273.1684	273.5488	0.4154	19.4327
	2	288.6913	0.0306	272.3805	272.3805	0.0000	9.6664	272.3805	272.8355	0.4109	19.4990
	3	280.6582	0.0308	273.3824	273.3824	0.0000	9.5774	273.3824	273.3824	0.0000	19.4054
	4	289.0498	0.0312	272.6250	272.6250	0.0000	9.6621	272.6250	272.9420	0.3434	19.4528
	5	288.3715	0.0310	272.0272	272.0272	0.0000	9.6483	272.0272	272.3894	0.3882	19.4929
5M_1SM	1	262.3282	0.0632	240.3917	241.1842	1.3213	14.9238	240.3917	245.3564	9.3118	35.6432
	2	261.9330	0.0386	241.3591	242.1214	0.4804	15.0638	243.0120	243.5730	0.5168	35.9292
	3	259.0225	0.0386	242.5177	242.7277	0.1065	15.2973	241.8448	243.3220	0.7231	36.1833
	4	261.4690	0.0307	240.4790	240.9937	0.6411	14.8871	240.7468	245.0673	9.1880	36.6266
	5	260.7353	0.0384	240.3992	241.7222	0.9695	9.9917	241.9285	242.6444	0.6015	36.1451
5M_2SM	1	235.1245	0.0623	220.6278	226.4494	16.4197	16.1606	222.0161	227.8172	15.3385	41.2393
	2	235.1747	0.0313	220.8738	223.0537	1.0737	16.1197	221.8335	223.2918	1.2553	40.9332
	3	229.2083	0.0313	221.7899	222.4988	0.5167	16.0383	222.2098	223.4241	0.7654	41.1394
	4	233.8881	0.0314	220.2564	220.8421	0.5986	15.9941	221.3231	223.3268	0.9852	40.9801
	5	233.0991	0.0540	219.9754	220.8627	0.9498	16.1148	221.6244	223.0454	1.0501	23.6129
7M_0SM	1	254.6882	0.0304	242.4338	242.4338	0.0000	14.8060	242.4338	242.4338	0.0000	27.5682
	2	250.0081	0.0410	245.4818	245.4818	0.0000	14.7488	245.4818	245.4818	0.0000	27.3785
	3	256.4996	0.0313	242.6528	242.6528	0.0000	14.6842	242.6528	242.6528	0.0000	27.4526
	4	255.4101	0.0649	241.0511	241.0511	0.0000	14.7499	241.0511	241.0511	0.0000	27.6607
	5	248.6818	0.0307	243.5022	243.5022	0.0000	14.7728	243.5022	243.5022	0.0000	27.4426
7M_1SM	1	209.7768	0.0392	193.8559	194.7651	1.4955	17.3898	193.8559	198.5136	14.5885	43.0624
	2	205.9090	0.0327	195.6275	195.9298	0.9561	15.4299	195.6275	200.1597	15.0316	43.1886
	3	210.3618	0.0358	193.6937	194.9435	1.7563	15.4975	193.6937	194.3820	1.1789	42.9255
	4	209.5234	0.0383	191.7907	192.7903	2.1074	19.0997	191.7907	191.8991	0.3596	43.4612
	5	203.3247	0.0395	193.3945	194.7770	2.8824	17.4613	193.3945	193.3945	0.0000	43.3335
7M_3SM	1	209.7768	0.0399	193.8559	195.4087	1.6873	18.6638	193.8559	198.2720	14.6468	55.5563
	2	205.9090	0.0818	195.6275	197.9038	2.0697	19.8322	195.6275	195.6580	0.1013	55.6462
	3	210.3618	0.0379	193.6937	194.1985	1.0642	16.4121	193.6937	193.6937	0.0000	55.0307
	4	209.5234	0.0414	191.7907	193.2901	3.3735	19.3125	191.7907	196.2689	14.8526	55.1037
	5	203.3247	0.0390	193.3945	205.5087	20.1819	19.0199	193.3945	193.5381	0.3194	34.9915

Table 5: Results of the problem with a size of 200 jobs. The times in the *Makespan*, *Minimum*, *Mean* and *SD* columns are in hours; the times in the *Runtime* columns are in seconds

Instances		CH		TS			SA				
		Makespan	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime
3M.OSM	1	610.6969	0.0546	610.6969	610.6969	0.0000	11.6536	610.6969	610.6969	0.0000	26.9725
	2	618.2209	0.0251	617.1143	617.1143	0.0000	11.5336	617.1143	617.1143	0.0000	26.1710
	3	612.2402	0.0308	612.2402	612.2402	0.0000	11.4893	612.2402	612.2402	0.0000	26.7530
	4	621.7478	0.0287	620.2715	620.2715	0.0000	11.5570	620.2715	620.2715	0.0000	26.4309
	5	609.7617	0.0231	608.9957	608.9957	0.0000	11.4902	608.9957	608.9957	0.0000	26.9878
3M.ISM	1	475.1093	0.0263	471.7436	472.1191	0.4401	22.6933	471.7436	479.1092	7.6362	68.5123
	2	477.9048	0.0603	471.2468	471.9302	0.2401	22.6548	473.1117	483.6300	9.6616	67.3367
	3	477.4655	0.0312	472.0025	472.7258	0.6660	22.4926	472.6483	484.9616	23.8086	68.0840
	4	479.1875	0.0247	471.9663	472.8837	0.5859	22.6134	473.0217	480.7373	8.6356	66.5417
	5	475.9334	0.0404	470.3520	470.6273	0.5089	22.4684	470.3520	478.4176	8.0885	67.2547
5M.OSM	1	376.7026	0.0344	364.2603	364.2603	0.0000	16.6387	364.2603	364.8951	0.4355	35.9272
	2	375.2287	0.0293	363.0670	363.0670	0.0000	16.7366	363.0670	363.6870	0.4682	36.0278
	3	375.7788	0.0803	363.4850	363.4850	0.0000	16.8953	363.5423	364.5287	0.7311	35.9640
	4	375.1305	0.0311	362.8194	362.8194	0.0000	17.0122	363.5539	364.6527	0.8867	36.0673
	5	375.7715	0.0463	363.1440	363.2403	0.1244	16.7135	363.5455	364.0364	0.3352	35.9389
5M.ISM	1	347.3744	0.0600	312.9199	318.6758	16.0221	27.8310	313.5613	315.3256	1.3798	70.5935
	2	345.2799	0.0618	309.4372	312.0476	1.0688	27.4148	313.3722	316.1666	2.0478	70.6948
	3	345.4187	0.0932	312.4194	313.4956	0.8222	28.0400	313.7314	316.0786	2.2296	72.3128
	4	345.5312	0.0539	310.2377	310.9459	0.7960	27.8582	311.4463	314.5155	1.5047	71.2066
	5	346.5785	0.0609	311.3266	312.3708	0.7526	27.8642	313.8304	316.1836	2.3819	69.1587
5M.2SM	1	324.1417	0.0623	286.2429	287.2472	0.7522	29.7462	287.6227	292.1140	5.1489	79.0525
	2	296.2285	0.0933	286.5722	288.0962	1.1941	29.8022	286.7811	296.5976	11.1815	81.0484
	3	297.6219	0.0621	287.2807	288.0123	0.8758	29.8568	290.2016	300.1582	22.5811	79.9020
	4	298.6041	0.0628	285.8562	287.6624	0.9854	29.5890	288.7849	291.6251	5.1575	78.8049
	5	297.7146	0.0620	286.7968	287.5773	0.7079	29.3720	287.9297	292.8025	8.0794	79.5265
7M.OSM	1	284.4007	0.0521	269.0363	269.0363	0.0000	23.9065	269.8208	270.2095	0.3224	46.8607
	2	281.7620	0.0947	268.7174	268.7174	0.0000	24.2373	269.0485	269.4013	0.2748	46.9606
	3	283.2690	0.0526	268.9316	268.9316	0.0000	23.8727	269.3798	270.1676	0.6618	46.8134
	4	283.8884	0.0614	268.1423	268.1423	0.0000	23.8865	268.2449	269.6019	0.7691	47.0023
	5	286.7668	0.0617	268.6130	268.6130	0.0000	24.0109	269.9190	270.8556	0.5712	47.1590
7M.ISM	1	254.6244	0.1047	241.2175	244.5401	8.6232	34.0152	243.2270	244.0669	0.9480	80.2414
	2	275.9227	0.0619	240.3600	240.3978	0.1194	33.4659	243.6727	244.6442	0.8133	79.4553
	3	273.8024	0.0612	241.5823	242.4222	0.8037	33.9789	243.3568	245.0867	1.0891	78.8974
	4	274.2597	0.0705	240.4790	240.8957	0.2540	33.4936	242.1266	243.5392	0.9304	81.0473
	5	272.5796	0.1042	240.4423	242.7479	1.3382	33.9789	241.7134	244.5859	1.2552	78.6485
7M.3SM	1	228.7206	0.0685	218.0070	218.1836	0.3734	39.1109	220.3398	221.8375	0.9839	98.4580
	2	228.6280	0.0761	218.4104	218.4590	0.1024	38.7604	220.6156	222.0513	0.9999	98.8739
	3	230.3203	0.0717	218.6018	219.0267	0.6712	39.1564	221.4655	222.8018	0.9853	97.6755
	4	231.2625	0.1066	217.1583	218.0822	0.5747	38.9724	219.4981	221.3019	1.1110	98.1279
	5	230.3251	0.0720	217.8907	219.0011	0.7133	38.7555	221.2889	222.6865	0.7205	98.8198

Table 6: Results of the problem with a size of 300 jobs. The times in the *Makespan*, *Minimum*, *Mean* and *SD* columns are in hours; the times in the *Runtime* columns are in seconds

Instances		CH		TS			SA				
		Makespan	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime	Minimum	Mean	SD	Runtime
3M.OSM	1	922.0249	0.0412	894.2153	894.2974	0.2596	29.0635	894.8026	895.6062	1.0120	74.0956
	2	920.9402	0.0497	889.6129	892.3676	5.8074	29.1757	889.7069	893.7688	6.1982	73.7959
	3	920.0205	0.0843	897.5197	898.7414	1.9670	29.3625	897.6329	900.6518	2.0737	72.9320
	4	918.3851	0.0420	898.0580	898.4184	1.1394	29.4052	898.0580	900.8251	2.4732	73.4393
	5	914.9315	0.0413	896.7431	896.8854	0.4500	27.8970	896.7431	899.0111	1.9898	73.4214
3M.ISM	1	705.4881	0.0515	690.1181	693.9593	2.9822	62.6282	695.4366	806.3621	97.9360	204.5540
	2	719.2026	0.0514	685.1343	691.7652	4.3498	62.4406	697.7179	778.1078	77.1791	205.7994
	3	697.3001	0.0520	689.8264	693.6974	2.7349	63.7698	695.2303	798.3670	72.7856	193.9472
	4	700.2192	0.0518	686.4001	693.1599	3.5407	62.4592	694.9814	752.8230	61.3302	194.5259
	5	697.2390	0.0902	688.4681	693.2746	4.2178	61.5758	704.7633	795.6446	62.5972	194.5523
5M.OSM	1	565.3211	0.0512	543.9577	544.2676	0.6041	39.3408	546.9563	547.6840	0.5297	93.4156
	2	562.8431	0.0545	543.7699	543.7699	0.0000	39.4342	544.4141	545.9603	0.8022	93.7407
	3	561.3163	0.0511	545.3331	545.5202	0.4320	39.6559	546.4238	547.5288	0.7468	93.7905
	4	567.4178	0.0508	543.1318	544.2348	1.1817	40.2247	546.2421	547.4303	0.6595	93.0120
	5	563.6573	0.0888	544.3338	544.3720	0.1209	40.2076	546.3263	546.8604	0.4209	94.0397
5M.ISM	1	486.7713	0.0588	462.3656	463.6064	1.0169	71.3375	465.4637	486.5314	33.4544	215.9639
	2	492.0460	0.0612	459.6149	461.2763	1.1955	71.2652	465.2157	480.1204	13.1236	213.2547
	3	485.4487	0.0618	463.2700	464.8647	1.0838	71.1677	468.3979	477.1987	10.9069	206.4383
	4	489.4659	0.0606	460.1203	462.2203	2.0149	69.9958	463.6468	477.7493	12.5040	200.6013
	5	488.7583	0.1019	460.1764	463.4548	1.9688	71.7848	464.8673	481.0859	23.4197	198.8405
5M.2SM	1	439.3567	0.0626	416.1155	419.9085	2.7101	76.1312	419.7785	442.5253	21.2987	213.1607
	2	459.4036	0.0621	419.9435	422.4627	2.0208	75.8664	423.4955	449.3970	23.9638	214.2611
	3	433.9988	0.0629	419.1807	424.0700	4.1603	75.1913	431.5684	453.2257	23.1423	213.2559
	4	461.2445	0.0942	418.1086	420.4623	1.6562	77.5264	424.1247	436.0239	14.5959	215.6529
	5	432.3696	0.0612	418.3248	420.9339	2.1877	76.0617	422.0659	445.4032	18.0896	233.4503
7M.OSM	1	424.8417	0.0603	405.4736	405.4736	0.0000	53.8105	405.4736	406.4482	0.6099	113.3088
	2	426.6334	0.0611	411.5749	411.5749	0.0000	53.9669	411.9107	412.3072	0.4323	113.8662
	3	429.1812	0.0614	406.4274	406.4274	0.0000	54.3710	406.4274	407.8311	0.6789	112.2728
	4	427.1738	0.0925	407.7310	407.7310	0.0000	53.3038	407.7310	407.9821	0.5586	113.6120
	5	421.9863	0.0596	408.9597	408.9597	0.0000	54.7315	408.9597	408.9892	0.0217	114.9966
7M.ISM	1	378.5763	0.0610	342.2166	343.8627	0.9945	80.6928	344.1155	347.1833	2.0293	217.9036
	2	377.0361	0.0606	342.1196	343.0732	0.7427	80.4833	346.7422	348.1661	1.1650	217.2354
	3	376.8013	0.1027	341.8305	343.8877	0.8906	80.9706	344.2719	346.9565	1.4553	207.8833
	4	377.4541	0.0620	340.8306	342.1301	0.7653	80.0113	343.3609	346.1228	1.4839	214.4024
	5	377.4895	0.0612	341.3634	343.4910	1.4232	79.9183	343.5486	348.8507	4.5218	205.0270
7M.3SM	1	335.7697	0.0725	310.8605	312.9856	1.6322	94.2364	315.8166	331.8358	12.4198	244.0876
	2	335.0990	0.1044	315.4745	315.7299	0.4188	94.2792	318.1286	330.2643	11.9789	245.5285
	3	338.8665	0.0735	313.2732	313.4687	0.4204	94.4032	315.2920	326.2952	12.2950	245.1113
	4	338.4425	0.0804	311.3792	314.0996	1.7315	92.3268	311.3792	321.9751	8.2198	247.3404
	5	334.5442	0.1133	310.4200	313.0651	1.4701	92.9518	315.1598	329.8820	16.9257	243.9868

Table 7: Percentage of times each method (rows) achieves the best result of the three for each problem size and for the four aggregated sizes (columns)

	Sizes				Aggregate
	100	150	200	300	
CH	0%	0%	5%	0%	1.25%
TS	95%	93%	100%	100%	96.88%
SA	95%	78%	23%	18%	53.13%

fact, over 96% of the instances.

Furthermore, if we look at the mean and the standard deviation for Tabu Search, we can see that in many cases the minimum makespan coincides with the mean and that the standard deviation is equal to 0. This implies that for the 10 times this instance has been solved, the same makespan has been obtained. On the other hand, it can also be observed that, for many instances, the minimum makespan of Tabu Search metaheuristic coincides with that of Simulated Annealing metaheuristic. More specifically, this happens in more than 55% of the total instances, which is significant considering the randomness of both algorithms and the fact that they follow completely different processes to reach these solutions. Both coincidences, between the makespans for the same instances in different runs of Tabu Search and between the best makespans of both metaheuristics, are probably a good indicator of the quality of the solutions.

As for Simulated Annealing algorithm, it also gives very good results for smaller problems, giving the best solution in 95% of the cases for the problem with 100 jobs and in 77.5% for the problem with 150 jobs. However, it drops below 25% as soon as the problem has 200 or more jobs. On the other hand, the Simulated Annealing results show a significant increase in the Standard Deviation column (SD) as the problem grows, reaching almost 98 hours for the instance *3M_1SM 1* in the largest problem. This makes the consistency of Simulated Annealing much lower, although its best makespan is very close to that of Tabu Search. Again, this makes Simulated Annealing a less attractive alternative for this type of problem.

If the results of the Constructive Heuristic are examined, it can be observed that its results are of lower quality than those obtained with Tabu Search. However, in this case, the quality of the solutions does not deterio-

Table 8: Key metric for all problem sizes (columns), for each type of problem, and for all aggregated problems (rows). All times are shown in hours

Problem	Problem size			
	100	150	200	300
3M_0SM	1.40%	3.62%	0.11%	2.69%
3M_1SM	2.29%	6.50%	1.20%	2.31%
5M_0SM	5.56%	5.33%	3.40%	3.68%
5M_1SM	18.23%	8.39%	11.17%	5.94%
5M_2SM	6.57%	5.71%	5.70%	6.44%
7M_0SM	8.76%	4.14%	5.71%	4.40%
7M_1SM	8.15%	7.29%	12.22%	10.48%
7M_3SM	8.15%	7.29%	5.43%	7.77%
Mean	7.39%	6.03%	5.62%	5.46%

rate as the problem size increases, but rather remains constant. To reflect this information more clearly, the key metric shown in Equation 20 is calculated for all instances and problem sizes. This information is presented in Table 8 and the average key metric for all instances per size is added in the last row (*Mean*). In this way, it is easier to see that the difference between one solution and another, far from getting worse as the problem size increases, improves slightly, with in some cases the same solutions being obtained for 200 jobs (Table 5, instances *3M_0SM 1* and *3M_0SM 3*).

$$\frac{|\text{Minimum TS makespan} - \text{CH makespan}|}{\text{Minimum TS makespan}} \quad (20)$$

Another important aspect to note when analysing the response of the Constructive Heuristic, and therefore Tabu Search, is that there is no deviation in their responses, but they are compared to the best of the solutions from 10 Tabu Search runs. This could be seen as a bias against the heuristic method and, therefore, this comparison does not imply that if both algorithms were run only once, Tabu Search would give better answers in all cases. Accordingly, it is important to pay attention to the deviation of Tabu Search solutions and, if necessary, to examine the behaviour of the algorithm. For this purpose, instances with deviations for Tabu Search that exceed 5% of the mean value of their makespan are selected and their makespan values

are examined in more detail (Table 9). The first two columns of the table indicate the size and the instance to which the results of the 10 Tabu Search executions correspond. The next 10 columns show the makespan of those 10 executions. Finally, the last column shows the makespan obtained with the Constructive Heuristic. In addition, the makespan of Tabu Search that exceeds the makespan obtained with the Constructive Heuristic is highlighted in bold, i.e. the results of Tabu Search that are worse than those of the Constructive Heuristic.

Table 9: Makespans for the 10 runs of Tabu Search and Constructive Heuristic (columns) for all problems (rows) with a standard deviation greater than 5% of Tabu Search mean. Bold numbers indicate Tabu Search makespans that are higher than the Constructive Heuristic for each problem

Size	Instance	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	CH
100	3M-1SM 3	257.43	257.43	258.61	257.43	258.61	257.43	257.43	328.12	258.61	257.43	262.64
	3M-1SM 4	258.07	258.07	258.07	259.61	255.31	326.88	255.31	258.07	256.85	258.07	260.58
	3M-1SM 5	327.24	253.65	253.65	253.65	253.65	253.65	327.24	253.65	253.65	253.65	259.56
	5M-1SM 3	162.57	162.57	181.24	181.24	181.24	162.57	162.57	181.24	162.57	166.17	194.46
	5M-2SM 1	156.23	182.51	163.28	156.84	157.45	156.84	182.51	156.23	156.23	157.45	164.94
150	5M-2SM 2	155.18	157.12	157.12	183.16	155.18	157.28	157.12	155.18	157.12	155.60	162.22
	5M-2SM 5	156.20	158.09	155.79	155.79	156.28	159.03	155.21	155.21	155.79	182.19	163.13
	7M-1SM 4	147.71	147.71	147.71	147.71	172.16	147.71	147.71	147.71	172.16	147.71	162.26
	7M-3SM 4	147.71	147.71	151.03	147.71	147.71	172.16	151.03	147.71	147.71	147.71	162.26
	3M-1SM 3	352.48	449.25	353.14	352.75	353.02	352.75	353.67	353.67	353.14	353.02	392.03
200	3M-1SM 4	354.10	451.02	352.72	352.68	352.93	353.87	354.50	352.68	352.20	352.68	366.41
	3M-1SM 5	352.28	350.41	349.84	352.28	351.65	351.21	448.81	351.66	351.21	351.46	360.64
	5M-2SM 1	222.17	221.27	221.14	221.27	220.63	221.14	221.27	221.14	221.27	273.17	235.12
	7M-3SM 5	197.28	201.41	193.39	197.28	193.39	193.39	243.50	194.53	197.40	243.50	203.32
	5M-1SM 1	364.26	312.92	313.12	313.68	313.63	313.43	314.25	313.68	314.23	313.56	347.37

Table 10: Average runtimes for each algorithm (columns) and for each problem size (rows). All times are shown in seconds

Size	CH	TS	SA
100	0.0392	6.7694	15.1344
150	0.0386	13.4668	32.5875
200	0.0590	25.6405	63.2078
300	0.0666	63.3357	170.2626

In the results, it can be seen that although the deviations for these cases are higher than 5% of the mean value, on average there is only one Tabu Search makespan that is higher than the makespan of the Constructive Heuristic. Only in three cases are there two solutions from Tabu Search that are higher than the one from the Constructive Heuristic. The reason for the high deviation is that even if only one or two results usually differ, they do so significantly. Furthermore, as can be seen, this happens only in 15 cases, less than 10% of the total, and mainly in the smallest size of the problem. This once again demonstrates the consistency of the solution obtained by Tabu Search, and confirms that in the vast majority of cases it produces makespans that are lower than those obtained by the Constructive Heuristic.

Finally, it is important to note the execution times of the algorithms. Table 10 shows the average execution times in seconds for each algorithm (columns) for each size of problem (rows). Looking at both metaheuristics (*TS* and *SA*), their average execution times increase as the problem size increases. This is more noticeable for Simulated Annealing, where the execution times are twice as long as for Tabu Search for small sizes and three times as long as for larger sizes. This confirms that the results of Simulated Annealing lose quality as the problem size increases and that Tabu Search always gives better performance.

However, the Constructive Heuristic stands out for its almost immediate response, which never exceeds 0.12 seconds (Table 3, 4, 5, 6). Furthermore, by looking at the average runtimes (Table 10), it can be seen that the increase in runtime with increasing problem size is negligible. However, the difference between a duration of less than a second for the Constructive Heuristic and a duration of just over a minute and a half in the worst case for Tabu Search is not considered significant for this type of problem.

Therefore, the algorithm that provides better results considering all the aspects analysed is Tabu Search, which not only produces the lowest and best results, but also with lower deviations and acceptable execution times for all the problem sizes considered. This, in the context of the real industry whose methodology has been replicated in the first block of the Constructive Heuristic, indicates that the results they currently obtain manually could be significantly improved by using this metaheuristic. In addition, each of the algorithms would improve the solution time of their planning, and they would be able to make much better use of the human resources they currently have working on planning.

Focusing our attention on the use of machines as support machines, a key feature of the problem addressed here, it becomes interesting to use this study to determine whether or not it would make sense from an industrial point of view to include machines in the role of SMs. With this objective in mind, we include a graphical representation (Figure 5) to facilitate the understanding of the extensive data. This graphical aid is intended to make it easier to interpret the complex results, which can be difficult to understand due to their density and vastness. This bar chart represents the four different problem sizes on the horizontal axis and the time in hours on the vertical axis. For each size, eight different bars are displayed, each corresponding to a particular resource configuration, as detailed in Table 2 and explained in the accompanying legend. Each of these bars represents the mean value of the makespan calculated from the five instances of each configuration. This average was specifically calculated using the minimum times produced by Tabu Search algorithm that gave the most favourable results in terms of makespan.

From this graph, it is easy to see the significant improvement that occurs when a SM is introduced, from three MM to three MM and one SM. However, the later cases show comparatively less pronounced changes. In order to deepen this analysis, and together with this graph, special attention will be paid to the problems *5M_2SM*, *7M_0SM*, *7M_1SM*, and *7M_3SM*.

Firstly, it is important to note that in some cases a certain pattern has been identified that differs from initial expectations. This occurs in cases with the same number of machines, but which do not represent the same type of resource, i.e. the number of MMs and SMs changes even though the total number of machines remains constant. In this situation, one would expect that using all machines as MMs would give better results, mainly by avoiding transport times. However, this does not happen for sizes of 100 and 150 jobs

Figure 5: Average makespan comparison for different problem sizes and resource configurations. The horizontal axis represents the four different problem sizes, while the vertical axis represents time in hours. Each of the eight bars per problem size corresponds to a specific resource configuration.

with instances $5M_2SM$ and $7M_0SM$ (Tables 3 and 4). After analysing the sequencing and assignment for these instances, it is observed that the size of the problem, the number of machines, and the presence of mandatory precedences significantly reduce the number of possible combinations and create unusual situations which, thanks to these results, can be taken into account in a real scenario. Thus, in situations similar to those presented here, it may be appropriate to use some of the resources with full capacity as support (SM), even though they have the capacity to be MM. In the rest of the cases, the results indicate that it is better to use MMs to perform full orders.

On the other hand, if the general effect of using SMs in the problem is analysed now, with instances $7M_0SM$, $7M_1SM$, and $7M_3SM$, the improvement that emerges from using one or more SMs while maintaining the number of MMs constant can be identified, that is, the gain between leaving the machines unused or using them to support the others. For this analysis, and given the random component of Tabu Search, the results are aggregated by comparing the average improvement between each problem, not between each instance. To explain the structure of the Table 11 and the information it contains, the problem of the smallest size, with 100 jobs, is presented. It is found that the mean makespan for the instances of problems $7M_0SM$ is 173.7765 hours compared to 150.1211 hours for problems $7M_1SM$ and $7M_3SM$. This is a difference of almost 24 hours when using one and three extra machines as support, an improvement of 13.61% when going from zero to one SM (column *Difference 0SM - 1SM*) and 0% when going from one to three SMs (column *Difference 1SM - 3SM*). These same figures for the remaining sizes can be seen in Table 11.

It can be seen that the use of support machines generally improves the makespan by reducing the time taken by the SMs to complete their jobs. However, the inclusion of a new support machine is not always significant, as can be seen from the change from one SM to three SMs, where no improvement is observed for problems of small size. Thus, taking into account the aspects considered in this work, as the problem size increases, other SMs can be progressively added to support the MMs. However, it should not be forgotten that many other important aspects for decision making are not included in these algorithms, such as maintenance costs or the cost of operators needed to keep the additional machines active.

Finally, it is worth noting the importance of using a good initial allocation procedure when no further allocations are to be considered, as is the case

Table 11: Average makespans for problems $7M_0SM$, $7M_1SM$ and $7M_3SM$ (columns) for all sizes (rows) and improvement percentage when introducing one SM (fourth column) or 3 SMs (fifth column). The times in the first three columns are given in hours

	7M_0SM	7M_1SM	7M_3SM	Difference 0SM - 1SM	Difference 1SM - 3SM
100	173.7765	150.1211	150.1211	13.61%	0.00%
150	243.0243	193.6725	193.6725	20.31%	0.00%
200	268.6881	240.8162	218.0136	10.37%	9.47%
300	408.0333	341.6722	312.2815	16.26%	8.60%

with the pre-established allocations in the industry used in this paper. As can be seen from the results of the heuristic procedure, which in its first block replicates the methodology of this real industry, the results for the cases $5M_2SM$ and $7M_0SM$ would indicate that it is better to use two MMs as support (SM), both in the size of 100 and 150 jobs (Tables 3 and 4). The results of the other two metaheuristics have shown this to be incorrect.

5. Conclusions

This paper presents an Unrelated Parallel Machine Scheduling problem with an additional feature, the existence of Support Machines. These machines have the same characteristics as the other machines, but their capacity is limited, so they cannot complete jobs. In this situation, these machines are used to support the others by executing jobs until they reach their own limit and then sending them to another machine with full capacity to finish them.

Three different algorithms have been carefully developed to address the challenges of production planning in this context. The first algorithm, a Constructive Heuristic, is inspired by manual problem solving practises within the production environment. It incorporates a second cycle to improve solutions, eliminate human error, and streamline the process. In doing so, it bridges the experiential wisdom of the factory staff with the expertise of the authors.

The other two algorithms, Tabu Search and Simulated Annealing metaheuristics, are tailored for the specific problem. These three methodologies

undergo rigorous testing with a diverse data set of 160 instances. These include different problem sizes and different numbers of machines of each type. The results are presented and analysed.

After comparing the results for the three methods, the first and most obvious conclusion is that, taking into account the makespans, Tabu Search gives better results for any problem size. It gives the lowest makespans for 97% of the instances.

In terms of execution times, the Constructive Heuristic is the one that gives the best results, never taking more than 0.12 seconds to solve any of the instances, compared to the minute and a half that Tabu Search algorithm requires and the 4 minutes that Simulated Annealing takes for the most complex instances. Given the industrial parameters that motivated this study, this would not be a real limitation, since planning is carried out for an average of 250 jobs and for much longer horizons than 4 minutes. However, it could be a limitation in other manufacturing environments where there could be much larger numbers of jobs with smaller planning horizons.

Therefore, for the environment from which the data was taken, Tabu Search definitely gives better results in acceptable execution times than the Constructive Heuristic. It is important to remember that this heuristic is based on the first of its blocks in the manual and real decision making that is currently carried out in the factory from which the data was gathered; therefore, these results show that the application of this type of metaheuristics would increase the productive capacity of the plant. However, as mentioned above, it is important to analyse these results thoroughly before deciding which tool could best adapt to different environments.

On the other hand, as far as the use of support machines is concerned, it is concluded that, in general, the use of support machines reduces the makespan, as long as the number of support machines is studied and appropriate for the size of the problem.

Similarly, for small-size problems with mandatory precedences that limit the number of possible combinations for problem assignment and sequencing, it is found that using some of the full capacity machines as support machines, far from slowing down the capacity of the plant, can improve production times.

These conclusions are, of course, subject to the indicators included here, and it is obvious that, in addition to these, the costs associated with the use of certain resources in real environments should also be taken into account. This is, in fact, a future line of work, the incorporation in these models of

the costs of using more or fewer machines, including, for example, the costs of maintenance, electricity, or the workforce needed to operate them.

In addition, it would be interesting to study the effect of increasing the size of the problem. This study has demonstrated the clear suitability of Tabu Search for sizes between 100 and 300 jobs, using real data from the wind tower manufacturing industry. However, it would be interesting to analyse how the results, especially the execution times, evolve for environments with larger problem sizes.

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